

1 **Genes that identify the HPV+ cancer cell line.**

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6 We demonstrate here through transcriptomic means specific enrichment of *Gpr107*, *Fam161a*, *Fam210b*,
7 *Tcam1p* and *Tmem121* in HPV+ head and neck cancer cell lines.

8 Citations

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